

Fig. 1: Density plot of all population-level effects of the β_μ parameters. Each density is cut off at 95%. The parameters are significant if their 95% CI intervals do not cross zero. From this plot we can observe that all parameters are significant, except for the β_μ parameter of milestone-2, which represents the cutpoint between the first and second milestone. The other cutpoints of the milestone predictor are significant.

Fig. 2: Density plot of all population-level effects of the β_α parameters. Each density is cut off at 95%. The parameters are significant if their 95% CI intervals do not cross zero. From this plot we can observe that the β_α parameters of `security-level`, `team-size`, `nr-unplanned-stories` are significant. The parameters of the other predictors are not significant.

Fig. 3: Density plot of all population-level effects of the β_ϕ parameters. Each density is cut off at 95%. The parameters are significant if their 95% CI intervals do not cross zero. From this plot we can observe that the β_ϕ parameters of team-size, dev-workload-points and milestone-10 are significant. The parameters of the other predictors are not significant.